

Supplementary files of chapter 3 The low FODMAP diet in adolescents functional abdominal in a non-guided setting: a prospective multicenter cohort study.

Supplementary table 1. Overview of endpoints

Endpoint	Instrument	T0	T1 4 weeks after start treatment
Abdominal pain	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X
Associated symptoms	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X
Defecation frequency and consistency	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X
School absence	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X
Use of pain medication	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X
Adequate relief	Binary question on adequate relief		X

Supplementary table 2. Logistic regression analysis to identify baseline factors predicting treatment success at T1.

Predictor*	Simple logistic regression		Multiple logistic regression	
	OR (95% CI)	p-value	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Sex (female vs male)	1.21 (0.63 – 2.31)	.570	1.25 (0.62 – 2.52)	.536
Age at inclusion (in years)	1.03 (0.87 – 1.21)	.771		
Ethnicity				
White (reference)				
Middle Eastern/North African	1.07 (0.86 – 1.32)	.550		
Afro-Caribbean	0.92 (0.72 – 1.17)	.483		
Other	1.00 (0.76 – 1.31)	.975		
First-line family member with FAPD	1.23 (0.62 – 2.41)	.555	1.26 (0.38 – 2.30)	.463
Diagnosis (IBS vs. FAP-NOS)	2.16 (1.04 – 4.48)	.038	2.52 (1.15 – 5.56)	.022
IBS subtype				
IBS-U (ref)				
IBS-C	1.85 (0.53 – 6.51)	.337		
IBS-D	2.03 (0.50 – 8.30)	.323		
IBS-M	1.48 (0.35 – 6.29)	.597		
Duration of symptoms (in years)	1.00 (0.92 – 1.08)	.943		
Including center (academic vs teaching center)	1.53 (0.87 – 2.68)	.141	1.45 (0.78 – 2.68)	.238
Mean abdominal pain severity at baseline	0.98 (0.73 – 1.32)	.877		
Mean abdominal pain frequency at baseline	0.97 (0.92 – 1.02)	.246	0.98 (0.93 – 1.04)	.981
Mean bloating at baseline	0.98 (0.87 – 1.11)	.778		
Mean flatulence at baseline	1.01 (0.89 – 1.15)	.897		
Mean defecation frequency at baseline	0.94 (0.79 – 1.12)	.459	0.93 (0.76 – 1.13)	.469
Mean defecation consistency at baseline	1.56 (0.46 – 5.34)	.475		
Mean nausea at baseline	1.00 (0.86 – 1.16)	.994		
Mean headache at baseline	0.99 (0.86 – 1.14)	.842		
Mean use of painkillers at baseline	1.05 (0.87 – 1.28)	.608		
Mean school absence at baseline	0.94 (0.76 – 1.16)	.573		
Mean loss of appetite at baseline	0.94 (0.80 – 1.09)	.393	0.94 (0.78 – 1.12)	.477
Child's expectancy of treatment at baseline	1.08 (0.91 – 1.28)	.406	1.00 (1.00 – 1.00)	.079
Mother's/parent 1 expectancy of treatment at baseline	1.00 (0.81 – 1.24)	.980		
Father's/parent 2 expectancy of treatment at baseline	1.03 (0.86 – 1.22)	.780		

*** For continuous predictors the OR should be interpreted as the change in OR with one unit increase in the predictor value.**

Supplementary table 3 Logistic regression analysis to identify specific symptom improvement associated with treatment success at T1.

Predictor*	Simple logistic regression		Multiple logistic regression	
	OR (95% CI)	p-value	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Change in mean abdominal pain frequency, hours	1.30 (1.10 – 1.54)	.003	1.27 (1.06 – 1.51)	.009
Change in mean bloating severity	1.35 (1.10 – 1.67)	.004	1.24 (0.94 – 1.64)	.119
Change in mean flatulence severity	1.33 (1.05 – 1.67)	.016	1.17 (0.89 – 1.56)	.261
Change in mean defecation frequency	1.00 (0.99 – 1.01)	.892	1.00 (0.99 – 1.01)	.910
Change in mean defecation consistency	2.31 (0.63 – 8.54)	.21	1.53 (0.36 – 6.63)	.563
Change in mean headache severity	1.20 (1.02 – 1.42)	.029	1.15 (0.94 – 1.41)	.180
Change in mean nausea severity	1.26 (1.04 – 1.53)	.017	1.10 (0.86 – 1.40)	.441
Change in mean loss of appetite severity	1.13 (0.94 – 1.36)	.196	1.02 (0.81 – 1.30)	.852

* For continuous predictors the OR should be interpreted as the change in OR with one unit increase in the predictor value.

Supplementary table 4. Logistic regression analysis to identify baseline factors predicting adequate relief at T1.

Predictor*	Simple logistic regression		Multiple logistic regression	
	OR (95% CI)	p-value	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Sex (female vs male)	2.50 (1.13– 5.54)	.025	1.18 (1.06 – 1.31)	.003
Age at inclusion (in years)	1.12 (0.93 – 1.34)	.221		
Ethnicity				
White (reference)				
Middle Eastern/North African	1.03 (0.89 – 1.19)	.708	0.97 (0.81 – 1.67)	.770
Afro-Caribbean	1.25 (1.04 – 1.50)	.014	1.10 (0.89 – 1.37)	.375
Other	1.20 (1.00 – 1.44)	.052	1.01 (0.79 – 1.29)	.929
First-line family member with FAPD	0.87 (0.46 – 1.64)	.669		
Diagnosis (IBS vs. FAP-NOS)	1.45 (0.75 – 2.82)	.272		
IBS subtype				
IBS-U (ref)				
IBS-C	1.06 (0.89 – 1.29)	.511	1.09 (0.92 – 1.30)	.301
IBS-D	1.11 (0.92 – 1.34)	.274	1.11 (0.93 – 1.33)	.239
IBS-M	1.19 (0.97 – 1.45)	.094	1.17 (0.97 – 1.41)	.109
Duration of symptoms (in years)	1.03 (0.96 – 1.10)	.416		
Including center (academic vs teaching center)	1.47 (0.80 – 2.70)	.212		
Mean abdominal pain severity at baseline	0.44 (0.31 – 0.63)	<.001	0.90 (0.85 – 0.95)	<.001
Mean abdominal pain frequency at baseline	0.85 (0.75 – 0.95)	.006	1.00 (0.99 – 1.00)	.212
Mean bloating at baseline	0.95 (0.83 – 1.08)	.441		
Mean flatulence at baseline	1.01 (0.88 – 1.17)	.919		
Mean defecation frequency at baseline	1.11 (0.90 – 1.36)	.326		
Mean defecation consistency at baseline	0.30 (0.06 – 1.44)	.131		
Mean nausea at baseline	0.95 (0.80 – 1.13)	.577		
Mean headache at baseline	0.94 (0.80 – 1.10)	.417		
Mean use of painkillers at baseline	1.15 (0.93 – 1.42)	.188		
Mean school absence at baseline	0.96 (0.74 – 1.25)	.767		
Mean loss of appetite at baseline	1.03 (0.88 – 1.21)	.684		
Child's expectancy of treatment at baseline	1.23 (1.00 – 1.53)	.052		
Mother's/parent 1 expectancy of treatment at baseline	1.17 (0.93 – 1.47)	.194		
Father's/parent 2 expectancy of treatment at baseline	1.01 (0.84 – 1.21)	.923		

* For continuous predictors the OR should be interpreted as the change in OR with one unit increase in the predictor value.

Supplementary table 5. All adverse events

Adverse events	N = 325
	No. of patients (%)
Adverse events	
All adverse events	13 (4%)
Serious adverse events	0 (0%)
All adverse events ‡	
Gastroenteritis	5 (1.5%)
Urinary tract infection	2 (0.6%)
Fatigue	2 (0.6%)
Dermatitis	1 (0.3%)
Viral infection - unspecified	1 (0.3%)
Headache	1 (0.3%)
COVID-19 infection	1 (0.3%)

‡ Adverse events are listed in descending order of frequency.